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Abstract: If you're using a video to teach English, it can be tempting to simply put the video on and hope that it makes sense to the students. Especially for lower-level learners (CEFR A0-B1), this is not appropriate. The video could overwhelm them and make them think that they really don't know any English at all, simply because it was made for native speakers and contains rapid, high-level speech. You'll want to make sure that you have a specific ESL learning objective in mind for the video section itself. Making a concrete goal for the video will simplify things so that the students know they are not expected to understand everything in the video.

Keywords: foreign language, video tutorials, interactive games, types of active education, hand-eye coordination, activity.

In order to produce quality personnel in the future, It is very important to teach our children a foreign language, namely English, from today important At the moment, ninety percent of world literature is in English considering how necessary English is in today's life we have enough According to world scientists, learning a foreign language is ten years old They agreed that it will be easy for the children. During this period, the child he learns the language not by understanding but mechanically, that is why he learns a foreign language It is easy to use and pronounce. In addition, three in kindergarten age. In children under the age of 2 years, the volume of the brain. It has been proven that it can be done much faster. Some scientists say the same they advise that a child should be taught a second language as soon as he is born , then child learns an additional language quickly and easily without difficulties.

Make sure that you have a plan for what the learners need to do before, during, and after the video that relates to your language goals for the lesson. Try to keep things integrated with the rest of the course and never simply put on a video to kill time.

Preview any questions that you will want them to answer and make sure that they have the background knowledge to understand the words in the questions. Consider pausing the video for "turn and talk" discussions with their peers, just after an answer is given in the video itself.

Whether adults want it or not, modern children cannot imagine their life without videos. Various devices have become ingrained in our everyday lives, and they largely determine the way an entire generation perceives information. Currently, parents are

not surprised that the first toy their children take in their hands is a tablet. But how does this phenomenon affect their learning processes?

- Firstly, children are visual learners.
- Secondly, such children are very pragmatic, and the most important question for them is “How to use the acquired knowledge in real-life situations?”
- Thirdly, if these children are interested in something, they will persist in achieving their goals. But it is not easy to interest them.
- Lastly, their thinking and perception are not focused on memorizing facts and details, but on where to find the necessary information and how to apply it in the future.

Thus, visibility plays a crucial role in the learning process. Things evoking vivid emotions and impressions are easier to remember. Acquiring knowledge is better during an interaction. Therefore, of course, video content such as YouTube videos, cartoons and educational videos dedicated to young students, play a significant role in building high-quality and effective learning. Especially when teaching a foreign language, videos are a great resource to learn English.

Learning English through video content – the role of videos in kids’ education

The use of videos in the process of learning a language is, firstly, an example of live conversation. However, these are not just audio recordings. In the videos, we see who is speaking. We see facial expressions and gestures, which help us understand the intonation and the situation in general.

These educational videos for kids learning English create a real-life language environment. Children begin to understand that they are the same girls and boys who have mums and dads, and they have the same life; they speak differently, yet they still understand one another.

Any visual sequence that accompanies speech makes the information closer to the viewer. Regional and cultural facts become not just a set of phrases but give rise to associations, thoughts, and a desire to learn more about the subject.

Visuals encourage you to go to the places in question, try the food (if the conversation is about the traditions of local cuisine), take part in a holiday or visit a museum. These country peculiarities become personally significant; they motivate people to learn English – to learn more, you need to know the language better.

The right choice of videos in English for children plays an important role. Channels such as YouTube, for example, allow you to have access to a vast amount of videos, most of which are in English. They can be divided as follows:

- Authentic videos – English movies for kids, cartoons for learning English, video blogs, amateur video stories by native speakers.

- Educational authentic video – like video stories created, for example, for teaching English-speaking children (native speakers). These are informative videos on a variety of topics and fields of science. For example, videos about natural phenomena, historical events, geographical discoveries, space exploration, biographies of famous people, etc.

- English educational movies for language learners – educational videos that introduce various aspects of the language, cartoons to learn English, educational videos that aim to teach English.

Introducing movies in English to kids can be beneficial for their language development, but the ideal time to start depends on various factors, including the child's current language proficiency, their exposure to the language, and their interest.

In short, as a result of using innovative methods in English language classes, students' logical thinking skills develop, their speech becomes fluent, and the ability to give quick and correct answers is formed. Such methods make students eager for knowledge. The student tries to prepare thoroughly for the lessons. This makes students active subjects of the educational process. As the educational system sets itself the task of educating a free-thinking, well-rounded, mature person, in the future, we future teachers will contribute by developing ways to effectively use innovative technologies.

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